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Investigations on the luminescence properties of quartz and feldspars extracted from loess in the Canterbury Plains, New Zealand South Island

D. Brezeanu^{1,2}, A. Avram^{1,2}, A. Micallef^{3,4}, S. Cinta Pinzaru^{5,6}, A. Timar-Gabor^{1,2*}

¹Faculty of Environmental Science and Engineering, Babes-Bolyai University, Cluj-Napoca, Romania

²Interdisciplinary Research Institute on Bio-Nano-Sciences, Babes-Bolyai University, Cluj-Napoca, Romania

³Helmholtz Centre for Ocean Research, GEOMAR, Kiel, Germany

⁴Marine Geology & Seafloor Surveying, Department of Geosciences, University of Malta, Malta

⁵Biomolecular Physics Department, Babes-Bolyai University, RO-400084 Cluj-Napoca, Romania

⁶RDI Laboratory of Applied Raman Spectroscopy, RDI Institute of Applied Natural Sciences (IRDI-ANS), Babeş-Bolyai University, Fântânele 42, RO-400293, Cluj-Napoca, Romania

*alida.timar@ubbcluj.ro

Abstract. The applicability of the single aliquot regenerative (SAR) protocol, by using the optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) signal of quartz as well as the post-infrared-infrared (pIRIR_{225/290}) signals of polymineral fine grains, was assessed for dating loess in New Zealand South Island. OSL signals of quartz grains displayed low sensitivity. The application of repeated irradiation/bleaching cycles did not result in an increase in sensitivity, however annealing in the 300-500 °C temperature range generated the sensitisation of both the 110 °C TL peak as well as the OSL signal, likely by activation of yet unidentified luminescence centres. After heating, the quartz signal is comparable to that of ideal samples, but the annealing is precluding successful dating. On the other hand, feldspar infrared stimulated signals displayed satisfactory properties, allowing estimation of ages ranging from 14±1 ka to 29±3 ka for the investigated deposit. It was shown that pIRIR₂₂₅ and pIRIR₂₉₀ methods have potential for dating loess in the South Island of New Zealand: (i) dose recovery tests were successful with recovered to given dose ratios with a less than 10% deviation from unity, (ii) constant residual values of about 4 Gy and about 10 Gy were obtained after exposures for 48 h in the case of pIRIR₂₂₅ signals and 96 h in the case of pIRIR₂₉₀ signals, respectively, (iii) while a slight dose dependence of the residual was reported, for a dose as large as 1600 Gy the residual values are about 9 Gy and about 19 Gy for pIRIR₂₂₅ and pIRIR₂₉₀ signals, respectively.

Keywords: quartz; feldspar; luminescence; sensitivity; loess; New Zealand

1. Introduction

A well-established high-resolution chronology from southern mid-latitude sites is needed for providing a consistent framework of the inter-hemispheric climate changes. As such, archives in New Zealand play an important role for palaeoclimate reconstruction in the Southern Hemisphere (Alloway et al., 2007). Loess deposits represent one of the most widespread Quaternary archives in New Zealand, as they are estimated to cover approximately 10% of the land surface (Eden and Hammond, 2003; Yates et al., 2018).

Despite the well-established chronology of the North Island, there are few dating studies on the South Island of New Zealand. It was shown that some of the Quaternary dating methods have partial or no utility for chronological studies on loess-paleosol deposits from South Island. As such, beside the limited age range of radiocarbon dating, previous studies have shown that both organic material and charcoal interbedded within loess may be contaminated by younger mobile organic compounds (Goh et al., 1978; Hammond et al., 1991). In later studies, Hormes et al. (2003) concluded that the radiocarbon ages reported by Almond et al. (2007) for Birdlings Flat loess at Ahuriri Quarry, Banks Peninsula, are inconsistent with the optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) ages as well as with the isochrone established by Kawakawa tephra. The variations recorded in magnetic susceptibility on loess paleosol sequences are usually allowing for secure correlations with marine isotope stages (MIS) chronology, as the signal is influenced by the climatic conditions. However, for soils in areas such as the eastern part of the South Island, where the mean annual rainfall is less than 1200 mm, Pillans (1991, 1994) concluded that fluctuations recorded in the magnetic susceptibility are shielded due to iron remobilisation. For Canterbury mean annual rainfall is 645 mm. Widespread tephra bed layers can play a crucial role for establishing chronological frameworks, but because of the long distance from the volcanic sources in North Island, South Island is poor in tephra marker horizons, with only two widespread tephra marker layers recognized in the loess deposits: the

1 Aokautere Ash Member of Kawakawa Tephra Formation ($22\,590 \pm 230$ ^{14}C yr BP, ca. 26 500
2 cal. yr BP – **Wilson et al., 1988**), identified in the upper loess units throughout most of South
3 Island (e.g. **Campbell, 1986, Eden et al., 1992; Almond et al., 2007**) and the Rangitawa
4 Tephra, dated at about 340 ka (**Kohn et al., 1992; Alloway et al., 1993; Pillans 1996**) and
5 detected only by microscopic grain counting (**Eden et al., 1992**).

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12 Optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) dating method has been successfully applied on
13 quartz and feldspars extracted from various sediments on both the Northern and Southern
14 Hemisphere during the last decades. The precision and the accuracy of the ages obtained have
15 increased due to the development of the single aliquot regeneration protocol (SAR) on quartz
16 (**Murray and Wintle, 2000, 2003**), as well as the versions of the protocol developed for
17 feldspars, especially the post infrared-infrared protocols, pIRIR₂₂₅ (**Buylaert, 2009**) and
18 pIRIR₂₉₀ (**Thiel, 2011**). However, relatively few luminescence dating studies have been
19 reported on sediments of various origins from South Island, New Zealand (e.g. **Berger et al.,**
20 **2001, 2002; Hormes et al., 2003; Litchfield and Lian 2004; Preusser et al., 2005; Almond**
21 **et al., 2007; Rowan et al., 2012; Sohbati et al., 2016**). For dating relatively young sediments,
22 the preferred natural dosimeter is quartz due to the higher bleachability of the signal. However,
23 there are few studies that reported luminescence ages using quartz (e.g. **Holdaway et al., 2002;**
24 **Nichol et al., 2003; Litchfield and Rieser, 2005; Rowan et al., 2012**), and there is evidence
25 that quartz from South Island suffers from major problems that limit its application, namely
26 the weak sensitivity of the signal, with the signal apparently arising from many dim grains and
27 the unsatisfactory behaviour in the SAR protocol (**Preusser et al., 2006**). The recent
28 developments of the pIRIR protocols based on the SAR procedure have increased the interest
29 in using feldspars. While a number of studies reported the use of infrared stimulated
30 luminescence (IRSL) dating method on coarse-grained K-rich feldspars (**Preusser et al.,**
31 **2005**), or on polymineral fine grains (e.g. **Berger et al., 2001, 2002; Hormes et al., 2003;**
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1 **Rother et al., 2009; Almond et al., 2001, 2007; Shulmeister et al., 2010**), the potential of the
2 pIRIR protocols for dating sediments in South Island was not fully explored. To our
3 knowledge, the only exceptions are the studies conducted by **Sohbati et al. (2016)** and **Borella**
4 **et al. (2016)**, which have applied the pIRIR₂₉₀ method on K-rich feldspars extracted from
5 palaeorockfall boulders and loessic deposits south of Christchurch.
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12 The aim of this study is to further explore the luminescence properties of quartz extracted from
13 a loess deposit from Canterbury Plains, in the South Island, and to assess the applicability of
14 two post-infrared-infrared (pIRIR) stimulated luminescence protocols on polymineral fine
15 grains extracted from the same samples.
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22 **2. Study site**

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26 Apart from the Ross (2.4-2.6 Ma) and Porika (2.1-2.2 Ma) glaciations, New Zealand has
27 undergone at least five glaciations during the Quaternary (Suggate, 1990). The most extensive
28 deposits of loess are located across the foothills of the Southern Alps and in the lowlands of
29 the Canterbury Plains (**Yates et al., 2018**). The most developed loess deposits, reaching a
30 thickness of >20 m, are located on the lowlands south of Timaru (south Canterbury) and on
31 Banks Peninsula (**Bell and Trangmar, 1987**). Based on mineralogical composition, the main
32 source material for loess deposits from Canterbury Plains is eroded from the Southern Alps
33 (**Raeside, 1964; Sparrow, 1948; Young, 1964**). Using thermoluminescence (TL), **Berger et**
34 **al. (2001)** dated loess deposits from the south Canterbury Plains and Banks Peninsula, reporting
35 ages ranging from 246±91 ka (oldest age reported for Barrys Bay) to 21.4±2 ka (youngest age
36 reported for Cust section).
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53 The study site (44.018870 °S, 171.882054 °E) is located in the southern Canterbury Plains, on
54 the eastern side of central South Island (Fig. 1). Modern Rakaia, Ashburton and Rangitata rivers
55 flow perpendicularly to the eastern coastal cliff in the Canterbury Plains, discharging into the
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1 Pacific Ocean. The coastline at the study site consists of a steep cliff, up to 20 m high and
2 comprising poorly sorted and uncemented matrix-supported outwash gravel, which is capped
3 by a few metres of loess and modern soil. The cliff is eroded by a series of wide coastal gullies
4 (locally known as dongas). The sampling site is located halfway between Rakaia and
5 Ashburton rivers, on the southern flank of one of these coastal gullies.
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40 **Figure 1.** The map of the Canterbury Plains. The studied site is represented by filled circle.
41 (map source: www.d-maps.com)
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45 For luminescence investigations, five samples were collected from the top section of the flank.
46 The uppermost sample was discarded from the analysis due to its proximity to the modern
47 disturbed surface. The uppermost three samples analysed (NZ 2, NZ 3 and NZ 4) were collected
48 at depths of 30 cm, 50 cm and 70 cm, whereas the last sample (NZ 5) was collected from a
49 depth of 140 cm. As such, according to **Berger et al. (2001)** they are expected to belong to L1
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3. Methodology

3.1 Sample preparation

Luminescence samples were collected in stainless steel tubes and were prepared under subdued red-light laboratory conditions. The material from the end of each tube was removed and used for gamma spectrometry measurements. The material from the inner part of the tubes was used for 63-90 μm , 90-125 μm , 125-180 μm , 180-250 μm quartz and 4-11 μm polymineral grains extraction. A treatment with hydrochloric acid (10% concentration) and hydrogen peroxide (10% concentration followed by 30%) was employed for calcium carbonate and organic matter removal. Finer (<63 μm) and coarser (>63 μm) grains were separated through wet sieving. Polymineral fine grains (4-11 μm) were separated from the finer polymineral fraction obtained after Stoke's law settling and centrifuging in distilled water (**Frechen et al., 1996; Lang et al., 1996**). The coarser (63-90 μm , 90-125 μm , 125-180 μm , 180-250 μm) grain fractions were obtained by dry sieving. In order to isolate the coarse quartz fraction from the polymineral mixture a density separation using heavy liquid was performed (2.62 and 2.75 g/cm^3). In order to remove any remaining feldspars and the outer alpha-irradiated portion of grains, the quartz-rich fraction was obtained by etching with hydrofluoric acid (40% concentration for 40 min) followed by a rinse with hydrochloric acid (10%) for 60 minutes to dissolve any insoluble fluorides that may have formed. For luminescence measurements polymineral fine grains were mounted on aluminium discs whereas for coarse quartz stainless steel discs were used.

3.2 Analytical facilities

All luminescence measurements were carried out using two Risø TL/OSL readers (model DA-20), equipped with a classic or automated detection and stimulation head (DASH) (**Lapp et al., 2015**). EMI 9235QA and PSM 9107Q-AP-TTL-03 (160-630 nm) photomultipliers were used for luminescence signals detection. Quartz signals were detected using a 7.5-mm-thick

1 Hoya U-340 UV filters while for polymineral fine grain signals a blue filter combination
2 (Schott BG3 + Corning 7-59, with transmission between 320-460 nm) was used. Beta
3 irradiations were carried out by ^{90}Sr - ^{90}Y radioactive sources mounted on the readers and
4 calibrated for both fine and coarse fractions using gamma-irradiated calibration quartz (**Hansen**
5 **et al., 2015**).

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11 The natural luminescence signal of the polymineral fine grain aliquots used for bleaching
12 experiments and residual dose measurements was erased by exposing the disks to window light
13 under natural conditions in March (latitude 46° 47' N).
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17 Raman spectra have been recorded using a Renishaw InVia Reflex Confocal Raman system
18 with an Leica microscope using the 100X (NA 0.9) long working distance objective. For
19 excitation, a Cobolt DPSS laser emitting at 532 nm was employed. Wavenumbers calibration
20 has been achieved using the internal silicon standard. An edge filter was employed for
21 removing the Rayleigh line and the spectra were recorded in the 50-1840 cm^{-1} range with 0.5
22 cm^{-1} resolution. The acquisition conditions were 1s exposure, 1 accumulation and 100% of the
23 output laser power (approx. 200 mW). A Rencam CCD was employed for signal detection and
24 data acquisition and processing has been achieved using the WIRE 3.4 and Origin 9.2 software.
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41 **3.3 Equivalent dose determination**

42 The single-aliquot regenerative dose (SAR-OSL) protocol (**Murray and Wintle 2000, 2003**)
43 was applied on coarse quartz grains. Full details on the protocol are given in **Table S1a**. Optical
44 stimulation was carried out with blue light-emitting diodes for 40 s at 125 °C. For analysis, the
45 signal integrated over the first 0.308 s was used after an early background subtraction from
46 1.69-2.30 s interval, unless otherwise mentioned. A preheat temperature of 220 °C for 10 s and
47 a cutheat (ramp heating) of 180 °C were employed. At the end of each SAR cycle, a high
48 temperature bleach of 280 °C for 40 s was performed. In order to check the robustness of the
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1 SAR protocol, intrinsic tests (recycling and recuperation) were included in every measurement
2 as well as infrared (IR) depletion tests (**Duller, 2003**).

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4 Equivalent doses measured on polymineral fine grains were carried out by applying two
5 elevated temperature infrared stimulation methods based on the SAR procedure, the pIRIR₂₂₅
6 (**Buylaert et al., 2009; Wacha and Frechen, 2011; Vasiliniuc et al., 2012**) (**Table S1b**) and
7 pIRIR₂₉₀ (**Buylaert et al., 2011a, 2012; Thiel et al., 2011**) (**Table S1c**) protocols. In order to
8 reduce the signal susceptible to fading by allowing recombination of near-neighbour trap and
9 centre pairs, a stimulation with IR diodes for 200 s at 50 °C was performed after a preheat of
10 60 s at 250 °C in the case of pIRIR₂₂₅ protocol and 320 °C in the case of pIRIR₂₉₀ protocol,
11 respectively. The signal of interest was recorded during a subsequent IR stimulation for 200 s
12 at 225 °C in the case of pIRIR₂₂₅ protocol and at 290 °C in the case of pIRIR₂₉₀ protocol. The
13 net signal used for analysis was integrated from the initial 2.5 s of stimulation minus a
14 background evaluated from the last 50 s. A high temperature bleach was performed for 100 s
15 at 290 °C (pIRIR₂₂₅ protocol) and 325 °C (pIRIR₂₉₀ protocol) at the end of each cycle of
16 measurements. The size of the test dose was 17 Gy for all measurements.
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39 **3.4 Dosimetry**

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41 High-resolution gamma spectrometry was applied to determine the radionuclide specific
42 activities using a well-type HPGe detector. In order for ²²⁶Ra-²²²Rn equilibrium to be reached
43 the samples were stored for 1 month before measurement. Annual dose rates were determined
44 using the conversion factors tabulated by **Guérin et al. (2011)**. An alpha efficiency factor of
45 0.08±0.02 was considered for the 4-11 µm polymineral fraction (**Rees-Jones, 1995**). The time
46 averaged water content was assumed to be 15% with a relative error of 25%. The water content
47 was chosen to represent the mean water content over the depositional history of the sediments.
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49 Similar values for water content were used by **Rowan et al. (2012)** and **Sohbati et al. (2016)**
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for sediments from Canterbury Plains and Banks Peninsula, respectively. The external contribution from beta, gamma and alpha radiation, as well as from the cosmic rays, was included in the total dose rates. The cosmic dose rate was estimated as a function of depth, altitude and geomagnetic latitude (**Prescott and Hutton, 1994**).

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Luminescence properties – quartz

We have checked the purity of the quartz mineral extracts and their crystallinity by conducting RAMAN spectroscopy on sample NZ 5 63-90 μm . **Fig. 2** compares the spectrum of the sample to that obtained on calibration quartz. The results confirm that our extracted material is indeed crystalline quartz, according to the characteristic sharp bands observed in all the recorded spectra, similar with the quartz calibration sample. The fifteen bands observed in the Raman spectra recorded with minimal acquisition time (1s) and 1 accumulation, resembled those observed by Krishnan since early Raman studies on quartz published (Krishnan, 1945). The observed bands from microcrystals are located at 128 (s), 206 (s), 265 (m), 356 (m), 394 (m), 404 (m), 452 (sh), 464 (vs), 696 (m), 793 (w), 804 (w), 1063 (w), 1082 (w), 1160 (m) and 1230 cm^{-1} (w).

Figure 2. Comparison of calibration quartz (filled squares) RAMAN spectra with that of the 63-90 μm quartz (filled circles) extracted from sample NZ5.

1 To check if the quartz extracted from the investigated samples is suitable for OSL dating, the
2 SAR-OSL protocol labelled in **Table S1a** was applied. **Fig. 3a** shows a typical OSL decay
3 curve for the natural signal, while in **Fig. 3b** the decay of the signal measured after a
4 regenerative dose of 100 Gy is compared to that of calibration quartz. Based on the comparison
5 to calibration quartz it can be observed that the fast component does exist in the OSL signal.
6 However, its intensity is very weak. All investigated grain sizes displayed low sensitivity, with
7 no more than 1500 cts recorded in the first 1.2 s of stimulation in the case of the natural signal
8 (see **Table S2**). A weak signal could result in obtaining an equivalent dose of low precision,
9 but it should not affect the accuracy of the result. As the signals were found to be above the
10 detection limit, we have attempted to apply the SAR protocol to the various grain sizes of
11 quartz that were available. However, significant sensitivity changes were observed to occur.
12 The response to the administered test dose was found to vary significantly from one cycle to
13 another, the response increasing significantly during measurement cycles (see **Fig. 3c**). As
14 such, the SAR protocol is not able to correct for sensitivity changes and a well-defined dose
15 response curve could not be constructed (see a typical example in **Fig. 3d**). Consequently,
16 equivalent doses could not be confidently determined using quartz SAR-OSL. Another
17 important observation was made while recording the TL signals during the preheat procedures
18 applied in the SAR protocol following laboratory given doses. Unlike the case of well-behaved
19 OSL samples, where well-defined 110 °C TL peaks are always observed, the TL signals
20 recorded for these samples displayed weak 110 °C TL peaks along with a second peak at 150
21 °C. While the existence of the 150 °C TL peak in quartz is well known (see e.g. **Chruścińska**
22 **et al., 1996, Veronese et al. 2004, Preusser et al., 2009**) we have never identified it visually
23 so far in samples that are displaying bright OSL signals due to the dominance of the 110 °C TL
24 peaks. **Fig. 3e** presents such a typical example for quartz from New Zealand for a heating rate
25 of 5 °C/s.

Figure 3. Representative luminescence behaviour of 63-90 μm quartz extracted from sample NZ 3. (a) the decay curve of natural CW-OSL signal (open squares); (b) comparison between the decay curve of a regenerated dose of 100 Gy (open circles) and the typical decay curve of a calibration quartz (open triangles); data is normalised to the number of counts collected in the first channel of stimulation (c) variation of the Tx/Tn ratio during SAR cycles; (d) representative sensitivity-corrected dose response curve. The sensitivity corrected natural signal is depicted as a star. Recycling and IR depletion points are represented as an up triangle and inverse triangle, respectively; (f) TL signal recorded during the preheat to 220 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ employed in a typical SAR cycle after irradiation with a regenerative dose of 100 Gy.

We have further tested the behaviour of sample NZ 3 63-90 μm quartz by performing a dose recovery test. Three aliquots were bleached with blue diodes twice at room temperature for 100 s with a 10000 s pause in between the two stimulations. A dose of 100 Gy was then administered and measured as unknown, using the SAR protocol as described in section 3.3.

Table 1 summarises the results obtained. One can observe that an increase in sensitivity occurs and sensitivity changes are not properly corrected by the measurement protocol, as observed from recycling tests. This results in an unsatisfactory recovered to given dose ratio.

Table 1. Results of dose recovery tests on NZ 3 63-90 μm quartz

	Signal sensitivity for the dose to be recovered (cts in 1.2 s)	Average signal sensitivity (cts in 1.2 s) for dose to be recovered	Signal sensitivity for 100 Gy in SAR (cts in 1.2 s)	Average signal sensitivity for 100 Gy in SAR (cts in 1.2 s)	Recycling ratio	IR depletion ratio	Recovered / given dose
aliq 1	3789		6268		1.13	0.78	0.81
aliq 2	1422	2571 \pm 684	3154	4472 \pm 930	0.83	0.76	0.60
aliq 3	2502		3993		1.11	0.78	0.94

The failure of quartz from New Zealand to accurately measure a given dose in the SAR protocol, as well as its poor OSL sensitivity, have been previously reported by **Preusser et al. (2006)** for sedimentary quartz of metamorphic origin from the forefield of Franz Joseph Glacier in the western part of South Island. The above-mentioned study attributed this behaviour to the short sedimentary history of the grains, as it was reported that sensitisation of the OSL signal was achieved by repeated bleaching/irradiation cycles.

In order to test whether OSL properties of the samples investigated here can be improved by the application of different irradiation and stimulation steps, we have conducted a dose recovery test on sample NZ 3 63-90 μm under the same conditions as presented above, except that the whole procedure was carried out subsequent to the application of three different treatments:

- (i) the repetition of 5 bleach (blue diodes stimulation for 100 s at room temperature) /dose (100 Gy) cycles,

(ii) irradiating the sample with a dose of 100 Gy followed by heating to 500 °C for 5 times and

(iii) simply by repeating for 5 times the heat treatment consisting of a ramp heating to 500 °C.

The results of the dose recovery test performed following these treatments are presented in

Table 2.

Table 2. Results of dose recovery tests after repeated cycles of bleaching and irradiation and heating and irradiation

Treatment Applied before the dose recovery test	Aliq no	Signal sensitivity for the dose to be recovered (cts in 1.2 s)	Average signal sensitivity for the dose to be recovered (cts in 1.2 s)	Signal sensitivity for 100 Gy in SAR (cts in 1.2 s)	Average signal sensitivity for 100 Gy in SAR (cts in 1.2 s)	Recycling ratio	IR depletion ratio	Recovered / given dose
Experiment (i) Bleach/dose (100 Gy) x 5	1	2685		2869		1.06	1.23	0.91
	2	1710	2858±718	2119	3015±565	1.14	0.89	0.66
	3	4180		4058		0.82	0.57	1.08
Experiment (ii) Heat to 500 °C/ dose (100 Gy) x 5	1	34665		41173		1.00	0.97	0.94
	2	39905	49960±12765	47148	60220±16152	0.98	1.01	0.95
	3	75311		92339		1.00	0.99	0.92
Experiment (iii) Heat to 500 °C x 5	1	10406		11556		0.98	0.99	0.97
	2	18612	20287±6244	24073	25794±8760	1.02	0.98	0.92
	3	31842		41754		0.98	1.01	0.94

Contrary to the findings of **Preusser et al. (2006)** we have not observed an increase in sensitivity or an improvement in the results of the dose recovery test - in other words, a better behaviour of the material in the SAR protocol following treatment (i), namely the application of repeated bleach/dose cycles. However, the sensitivity is increased by one order of magnitude following dosing and annealing, with the heat treatment accounting for most of the effect, as it can be seen from the results of experiment (iii), where irradiations have not been carried out. Following the application of the annealing to 500 °C, the behaviour of the OSL signals in the SAR protocol is improved, with satisfactory recycling and dose recovery tests results (**Table 2**).

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Another important observation is that significant sensitisation of the 110 °C TL signals was observed following annealing to 500 °C (see **Fig. S1** and **Fig. S2**). During experiment (ii) presented above it was observed that, while the 110 °C peak is weak in intensity during the first TL recorded (see **Fig. S2a**), once the sample was heated to 500 °C the TL glow curve shape changes dramatically. In the second TL/dose measurement cycle the 110 °C TL peak is well represented, and the glow curve is repetitive during subsequent irradiation read-out steps in the annealing process (see **Fig. S2b**). In the case of the dose recovery test without previous annealing, a composite 110-150 °C peak is observed in the low temperature region during the preheat of the signals (see **Fig. S2c**), and the OSL signals are weak in intensity (see **Fig. S2e**). If the sample is annealed to 500 °C before the dose recovery test, the OSL signals increase by one order of magnitude (see **Fig. S2f**) and so does the 110 °C TL peak (see **Fig. S2d**). As such, annealing the sample to 500 °C results in the sensitisation of both the 110 °C TL peak as well as the OSL fast component. While the heat treatment is making the quartz signal comparable to that employed in standard OSL dating, the annealing removes the desirable natural signal precluding successful dating of the material.

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The effect of repeating the annealing cycles on the OSL signal is shown in **Fig. 4** for the response of sample NZ 3 63-90 µm quartz to a dose of 100 Gy. The sample was bleached (room temperature blue diode stimulation for 100 s, pause of 10000 s, room temperature blue diode stimulation for 100 s) and then subjected repeatedly to the following measurement cycle: irradiation (100 Gy), preheat for 10 s to 220 °C, OSL measurement (blue diode stimulation at 125 °C), annealing (TL measurement) to 500 °C. Data presented in **fig. 4** show that the first thermal treatment enhances the sensitivity by one order of magnitude and subsequent annealing treatments do not have a further significant effect.

Figure 4. The OSL signal sensitisation after repeated annealing to 500°C. The luminescence signal intensities were measured after an irradiation to 100 Gy and a preheat to 220°C for 10 s. The OSL signal recorded before the first annealing is presented as an open square whereas the luminescence signals recorded following repeated annealing irradiation cycles are represented as solid squares.

The effect of varying the annealing temperature was tested as well. Aliquots of sample NZ 3 63-90 µm quartz were bleached and subjected to the following measurement steps: irradiation with 100 Gy, preheat for 10 s at 220 °C, OSL measurement (for 40 s at 125 °C), anneal to T_a (ramp heating to a temperature between 225 °C and 525 °C), irradiation with 100 Gy, preheat for 10 s at 220 °C, OSL measurement (for 40 s at 125 °C). As such, the OSL response after annealing can be compared to the OSL response before the application of the thermal treatment. This was carried out on three aliquots for each anneal temperature employed and the results of the average ratio between the post annealing and pre-annealing signals are presented in **Fig. 5**.

Figure 5. Sensitivity increase of the OSL signal as function of the annealing temperature. The dotted line represents an exponential dependence.

An exponential increase is reported as a function of annealing temperature, significant sensitisation occurring for heating temperatures above about 350 °C. This sensitisation with heating is intriguing, given the fact that the quartz analysed should have an important metamorphic (sub-greenschist) component from the Eastern greywacke basement rocks. As such, the crystal should have been subjected to moderate heating 300-100 Ma ago. Poor OSL properties of metamorphic quartz were also reported by **Guralnik et al., 2015**, with the authors inferring that only samples from a low-grade metamorphic context (heated to less than about 380 °C) are displaying satisfactory OSL properties.

Sensitisation by heating, and not due to pre-dose activation was previously reported to occur in partially fired (i.e. annealed only to moderate temperatures) quartz (**Yang and McKeever, 1990; Bøtter-Jensen et al., 1994**). However, a physical mechanism was not proposed as it was concluded that it is not possible to distinguish between a model that calls for the creation of luminescence centers or one that calls for the removal of non-luminescence centers due to annealing (**Bøtter-Jensen et al., 1994**). In a later multi spectroscopic study **Schilles et al., 2001**

1 concluded that luminescence is generally sensitized in quartz by heating to 500 °C or more by
2 the removal of oxygen vacancy E`centres, considered as luminescence competitors. This
3 mechanism cannot account for the observations made here, as sensitisation is observed also in
4 the 300-400°C temperature range where a heat treatment following irradiation is known to
5 increase the intensity of E`centres (see e.g. **Toyoda and Hattori, 2000**).

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11 The dependency presented is suggestive not only of the thermal activation curves presented by
12 **Yang and McKeever (1990)** for their as received Arkansas quartz, but also of the annealing
13 temperature dependence of the C band (3.4 eV) for radioluminescence signals reported by
14 **Martini et al. (2014)** for natural quartz. Consequently, the results presented indicate that the
15 heating process is most likely affecting the luminescence pathway and not the trapping process,
16 by the creation of recombination centres. Investigations for gaining further understanding on
17 these matters by employing electron spin resonance measurements are currently underway.

31 **4.2 Luminescence properties – polymineral grains**

32 **4.2.1. Equivalent doses**

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34 Unlike OSL signals of quartz, the infrared stimulated luminescence signals of polymineral fine
35 grains displayed a satisfactory behaviour in the SAR protocol. Equivalent doses were obtained
36 by interpolating the natural sensitivity corrected luminescence signal on the dose response
37 curve constructed for each sample using both pIRIR protocols. **Fig. 6** shows a representative
38 growth curve for sample NZ 4 using pIRIR₂₂₅ (**Fig. 6a**) and the pIRIR₂₉₀ (**Fig. 6b**) protocols,
39 respectively. The insets of **Fig. 6** present the comparison of decay curves of the natural signals
40 to those measured following regenerative doses.

Figure 6. Representative sensitivity-corrected dose response curves constructed for one aliquot from sample NZ 4 on polymineral fine (4-11 μm) grains using (a) pIRIR₂₂₅ and (b) pIRIR₂₉₀ protocol. The sensitivity corrected natural signals are depicted as stars interpolated on the dose response curves for indicating the equivalent doses. The recycling point is represented as an inverse triangle. Inset show typical decay curves of natural CW-OSL signals (open squares) in comparison to a regenerated signals (open circles) induced by a beta dose approximately equal to the equivalent dose.

The dose response curves were best fitted by a sum of two saturating exponential functions. The values for the equivalent doses range from 64 ± 2 Gy to 92 ± 23 Gy in the case of pIRIR₂₂₅ protocol and from 83 ± 3 Gy to 120 ± 6 Gy in the case of pIRIR₂₉₀ protocol, respectively. The measured equivalent doses along with the results of recycling and recuperation tests for each sample are shown in **Table S3**.

4.2.2. Residual signals

It is well known that the post-IR IRSL signals are difficult to bleach, as residual doses of a few Gys have been reported even after prolonged exposure to daylight or light in a solar simulator (e.g Buylaert et al., 2011b, 2012; Stevens et al., 2011; Murray et al., 2012, 2014; Yi et al., 2016, 2018; Sohbaty et al., 2016; Veres et al., 2018; Avram et al., 2020). Also, by measuring samples of modern dust and samples with an equivalent dose smaller than 1 Gy collected from

1 Chinese Loess Plateau, **Buylaert et al. (2011b)** have reported a residual average dose of 4 Gy
2 for pIRIR₂₂₅ protocol and 11 Gy when using the pIRIR₂₉₀ protocol.
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4 In order to quantify residual values, four fresh aliquots from each sample were exposed to
5 window for 30 days to remove the natural signal and quantify the residual level. Residual doses
6 measured using the pIRIR₂₂₅ protocol range from 3.3±0.4 Gy to 3.7±0.3 Gy while the values
7 obtained using the pIRIR₂₉₀ protocol are from 4.1±0.6 Gy to 13.6±2.5 Gy. The values obtained
8 on each sample are presented in **Table S4** and plotted against the measured equivalent dose in
9 **Fig. S3**.
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18 In order to check whether this is indeed the minimum residual level that can be achieved as
19 function of exposure time, sets of five fresh aliquots of sample NZ5 were exposed to window
20 light for different periods of time (from 0.5 h to 192 h). The results are shown in **Fig. 7**. In the
21 case of pIRIR₂₂₅ protocol, a constant residual dose of 3.7±0.5 Gy is achieved after 48 h of
22 exposure, while in the case of the pIRIR₂₉₀ signals residual values reach a constant value of
23 9.8±0.5 Gy only after a bleaching time of 96 h. These results are in line with the values obtained
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56 **Figure 7.** Residual doses measured using pIRIR₂₂₅ (up triangle) and pIRIR₂₉₀ (diamond) after
57 different bleaching times. The natural signal was bleached under natural conditions under
58 window light. The shortest bleaching time was 0.5 h while the longest was 192 h.
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Several studies have reported that the magnitude of the residual dose is dependent on the equivalent dose (e.g. **Sohbati et al., 2012; Buylaert et al., 2012, Yi et al., 2016**), suggesting a possible dose dependency of the residual. For the different samples investigated here, the residual doses measured after 30 days of exposure do not differ significantly (see **Table S4**), and neither do the equivalent doses. As such, in order to investigate whether the residual signal is dose dependent, eight bleached aliquots of samples NZ2, NZ3 and NZ 4 were irradiated with different beta doses of 400 Gy, 800 Gy and 1600 Gy and subsequently exposed to windowlight. After an exposure of 30 days, four aliquots from each sample were measured using pIRIR₂₂₅ protocol, whereas for the other four aliquots the pIRIR₂₉₀ protocol was used. The results are displayed in **Fig. 8**. An increase of the residual dose with the size of the previously given dose can be observed in the case of both pIRIR₂₂₅ and pIRIR₂₉₀ protocols. The magnitude of the residuals range from 5.9 ± 0.7 Gy (for a dose of 400 Gy) to 8.9 ± 1 Gy (for a dose of 1600 Gy) in the case of pIRIR₂₂₅ and from 13.9 ± 1.2 Gy (for a dose of 400 Gy) to 18.5 ± 1.7 Gy (for a dose of 1600 Gy) in the case of pIRIR₂₉₀, respectively.

Figure 8. Residual dose as a function of previously given dose.

1 We compare the data obtained for 1600 Gy (8.9 ± 1 Gy for pIRIR₂₂₅ and 18.5 ± 1.7 Gy for
2 pIRIR₂₉₀) to the values obtained in the bleaching experiment for the natural signals
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4 (corresponding to a measured equivalent dose of about 60 to 120 Gy), namely average values
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6 on all samples of 3.5 ± 0.2 Gy for pIRIR₂₂₅ and 9.2 ± 2.0 Gy for pIRIR₂₉₀, respectively. We
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8 conclude that (i) different doses accrued by the mineral grain before the bleaching event should
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10 not result in dramatically different residual doses and (ii) performing bleaching experiments on
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12 natural samples instead of using a modern analogue should not result in an offset of more than
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14 a few Gys. As such, bleaching corrections should not cause significant inaccuracies unless very
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16 young samples are dated. However, since a dose dependence is reported, and since it remains
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18 questionable whether the conditions in the laboratory fully reproduce the bleaching process in
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20 nature, it is advisable to measure a modern analogue for residual dose estimation as well. Here,
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22 a modern sample was collected from a nearby site (latitude 44.014973° S, longitude
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24 171.891569° E). Following the same methodology, an equivalent dose of 7.5 ± 0.5 Gy was
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26 measured using pIRIR₂₂₅ protocol while using pIRIR₂₉₀ protocol a dose of 22.8 ± 1.5 Gy was
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28 obtained. Based on the results of the laboratory experiments presented above, we consider these
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30 residual doses as maximum values. As such we have chosen to perform residual corrections
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32 using both laboratory obtained values, as well as by the modern analogue approach (see **Table**
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46 **4.2.3. Dose recovery**

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48 In order to further check the reliability of the measurement protocol, a dose recovery test
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50 (**Murray, 1996; Wallinga et al., 2000**) was performed on five aliquots from each sample using
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52 both pIRIR protocols. The natural signal was bleached by exposing fresh aliquots to window
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54 for one month. The aliquots were subsequently irradiated with laboratory known doses, chosen
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56 to approximate the measured equivalent dose. The dose recovery ratios were obtained by
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dividing the measured recovered dose to the value of the given dose. The measured residual doses were subtracted from the recovered dose prior to dose recovery ratio calculation. The results of the dose recovery tests using pIRIR₂₂₅ and pIRIR₂₉₀ protocols respectively are shown in **Fig. 9**.

Figure 9. Dose recovery test results for polymineral fine grains using pIRIR₂₂₅ (open triangles) and pIRIR₂₉₀ (open diamonds) protocols. The given irradiation dose was chosen to match the equivalent dose of each sample. The solid line indicates the ideal 1:1 dose recovery ratio while the dashed lines bracket a 10% variation from unity.

Dose recovery ratios obtained for the pIRIR₂₂₅ protocol range from 0.97 ± 0.02 (NZ 2) to 1.03 ± 0.01 (NZ 5) while for pIRIR₂₉₀ they range from 1.02 ± 0.04 (NZ 2) to 1.09 ± 0.05 (NZ 3), suggesting that both pIRIR₂₂₅ and pIRIR₂₉₀ protocols can successfully recover the laboratory doses given.

4.2.4. Anomalous fading tests

The greatest disadvantage of using feldspars as luminescence dosimeters is the loss of the signal during burial time. This loss of the signal is known as anomalous fading and can be usually quantified in terms of fading rates (percentage of the signal lost per decade; **Aitken, 1985**). **Thiel et al. (2011)** have reported for the first time a natural pIRIR₂₉₀ signal in saturation

1 for a sample collected below the B/M boundary and concluded that pIRIR₂₉₀ signal is a stable
2 signal and the pIRIR₂₉₀ ages do not need any further fading correction. Similar observations
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4 have been made by other researchers for pIRIR₂₉₀ protocol on both polymineral fine grains and
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6 K-feldspars (e.g. **Buylaert et al., 2011b; Thomsen et al., 2011; Veres et al., 2018; Avram et**
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8 **al., 2020**). Based on laboratory fading experiments, other studies reported fading rates of
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10 <1%/decade for pIRIR₂₉₀ (e.g. **Thiel et al., 2011; Stevens et al., 2011; Murray et al., 2014;**
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12 **Balescu et al., 2019**) and suggested that such low values are laboratory artefacts and do not
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14 reflect the instability of the signal in natural conditions (e.g. **Thiel et al., 2011; Buylaert et al.,**
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16 **2012; Avram et al., 2020**). Similar low fading rates have been reported on K-feldspars
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18 extracted from palaeorockfall boulders and loess from Banks Peninsula, South Island, New
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20 Zealand (**Sohbati et al., 2016**).

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26 On the other hand, in the case of pIRIR₂₂₅ signals it remains debatable whether the signals are
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28 affected by fading. Some studies reported g-values >1%/decade (**Buylaert et al., 2009; Zhang**
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30 **et al., 2018**) while other works reported fading rates of <1%/decade (**Vasiliniuc et al., 2012;**
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32 **Avram et al., 2020**). Therefore, the stability of the pIRIR₂₂₅ signal was checked by an
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34 anomalous fading test performed on three 4-11 µm polymineral fine grain aliquots of samples
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36 NZ 2, NZ 4 and NZ 5 (**Table S5**). The fading measurements were carried out on the same
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38 aliquots previously used in the dose recovery test. Each 4-11 µm polymineral aliquot was
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40 irradiated with a beta dose of 100 Gy. A test dose of 17 Gy was used. Four consecutive prompt
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42 reads-out were carried out prior to storage. The aliquots were preheated before storage. The
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44 maximum time delay was 38 days (912 h). Three consecutive prompt measurements were
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46 employed after the read-out corresponding to the longest storage time (see **Fig. S4** that presents
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48 individual results obtained on all aliquots). A fading rate <1%/decade was obtained for sample
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50 NZ 2 and NZ 5, while for sample NZ 4 a g-value of 2.28±0.44 %/decade was obtained.
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52 Therefore, the pIRIR₂₂₅ and pIRIR₂₉₀ ages presented in this study are not corrected for fading,
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except for sample NZ 4, for which a fading correction using the R Luminescence-package (Dietze et al., 2013) according to Huntley and Lamothe (2001) method was carried out.

5. Luminescence ages

Luminescence ages obtained based on pIRIR protocols along with the dosimetry information are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Summary of the pIRIR₂₂₅ and pIRIR₂₉₀ ages considering: ⁽¹⁾ the residual dose estimated based on a modern analogue sample, ⁽²⁾ the residual dose measured after laboratory bleaching. ^(*) indicates the age is corrected for fading. Uncertainties were determined following Aitken and Ailred (1972). A 15% water content was assumed with a relative error of 25%. Errors quoted on equivalent doses and specific activities represent random uncertainties. The uncertainties quoted for the ages represent total (random and systematic) errors computed in quadrature.

Sam ple code	Dep th (cm)	ED (Gy)		Specific activities (Bq/kg)			Total dose rate (Gy ka ⁻¹) pIRIR _{225/290} pfg	Ages (ka) ⁽¹⁾		Ages (ka) ⁽²⁾	
		pIRIR 225 pfg	pIRIR 290 pfg	K-40	Ra- 226	Th- 232		pIRIR ₂₅ pfg	pIRI R ₂₉₀ pfg	pIRIR ₂₅ pfg	pIRI R ₂₉₀ pfg
NZ 2	30	57±2	60±4	635±17	36±1	39±1	4.2±0.1	14±1	14±1	15±1	18±2
NZ 3	50	59±2	63±4	607±17	27±2	24±1	3.4±0.1	17±1	18±2	18±2	24±2
NZ 4	70	76±3	100±7	599±16	26±1	27±1	3.4±0.1	25±2 ^(*)	29±3	26±2 ^(*)	32±3
NZ 5	140	85±3	91±6	604±16	35±1	37±2	4.0±0.1	22±2	25±3	23±2	28±3

Only the ages obtained by residual dose correction using the modern analogue technique are represented as function of depth in Fig. 10. The pIRIR₂₂₅ ages range from 14±1 ka to 25±2 ka whereas the pIRIR₂₉₀ ages are slightly higher than pIRIR₂₂₅ ages, but still in agreement within errors for all samples. The pIRIR₂₉₀ ages vary between 14±1 ka and 29±3 ka.

Figure 10. pIRIR₂₂₅ (open triangles) and pIRIR₂₉₀ (open diamonds) luminescence ages plotted as function of depth.

The pIRIR ages increase down-section, except for an age reversal between the sample NZ 4 and NZ 5. Such age reversals have been previously reported by others in the Canterbury region (e.g. Berger et al., 2001; Almond et al., 2007; Rowan et al., 2012). The ages suggest that loess from this site was deposited during the last glacial maximum of the Otira glaciation that occurred between 18-24 ka (Alloway et al., 2007).

6. Summary and conclusions

The difficulty of obtaining reliable luminescence chronologies for loess in New Zealand South Island is well known. In this context, the applicability of SAR-OSL protocol on quartz as well as the feldspar SAR based pIRIR₂₂₅ and pIRIR₂₉₀ protocols on polymineral fine grains was investigated on four loess samples collected from the Southern Canterbury Plains. Although the purity and crystallinity of quartz extracts was confirmed by RAMAN spectroscopy, OSL signals displayed low sensitivity and significant sensitivity change during the measurement cycles. It was shown that sensitisation of the OSL signal as well as that of the 110 °C TL peak

1 could be achieved by annealing in the 300-500 °C range, likely by the activation of
2 luminescence centres. However, the same effect could not be achieved by repeated irradiation
3 and bleaching cycles as previously suggested. While equivalent doses could not be securely
4 obtained using quartz, the application of pIRIR₂₂₅ and pIRIR₂₉₀ methods were successful: (i)
5 dose recovery tests resulted in satisfactory results for both these protocols, results being
6 consistent to unity at a 95% confidence level (ii) fading rates of pIRIR₂₂₅ signals were generally
7 negligible, with measured values of less than 1% (iii) although pIRIR₂₉₀ signals are more
8 difficult to bleach than pIRIR₂₂₅ signals, constant residual values of about 4 and about 10 Gy
9 were achieved after exposure under window light exposure for 48 h in the case of pIRIR₂₂₅ and
10 96 h in the case of pIRIR₂₉₀ signals, respectively (iv) a dependence of the residual on the
11 previous given dose was observed, however, for a dose as large as 1600 Gy the residuals
12 obtained for the two methods are about 9 and about 19 Gy, respectively. Thus, the equivalent
13 dose of the sample used in the bleaching experiment should not have a significant effect when
14 the residual dose is determined by laboratory experiments. The ages obtained by the application
15 of the two pIRIR protocols are generally in agreement, with values ranging from 14±1 ka to
16 29±3 ka, suggesting that loess from the investigated site was deposited during the last glacial
17 maximum.

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Table S1. Quartz SAR-OSL and polymineral pIRIR protocols used for equivalent dose measurements in this study. (a) quartz SAR-OSL (b) pIRIR₂₂₅ and (c) pIRIR₂₉₀.

step	a. SAR protocol	b. pIRIR₂₂₅	c. pIRIR₂₉₀
1	Dose	Dose	Dose
2	Preheat (125 °C; 10s)	Preheat (250 °C; 60s)	Preheat (320 °C; 60s)
3	Blue OSL (125 °C; 40s)	IRSL (50 °C; 200s)	IRSL (50 °C; 200s)
4	Test dose (17Gy)	IRSL (225 °C; 200s)	IRSL (290 °C; 200s)
5	Cutheat (180 °C)	Test dose (17Gy)	Test dose (17Gy)
6	Blue OSL (125 °C; 40s)	Preheat (250 °C; 60s)	Preheat (320 °C; 60s)
7	Blue OSL (280 °C; 40s)	IRSL (50 °C; 200s)	IRSL (50 °C; 200s)
8		IRSL (225 °C; 200s)	IRSL (290 °C; 200s)
9		IRSL (290 °C; 100s)	IRSL (325 °C; 100s)

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Table S2. The average luminescence signal intensities of the natural and a beta dose of 100 Gy, recorded during the first 1.2 s of stimulation. Number of measured aliquots represents the number of aliquots that were taken into account for averaging the OSL signal. Tx/Tn maximum is the average of the maximum Tx/Tn ratio obtained for each aliquot measured using the SAR-OSL protocol.

Sample code	Grain size (µm)	Number of measured aliq	Natural signal intensity from 1.2 s	100 Gy signal intensity from 1.2 s	Tx/Tn maximum
NZ 2	90-125	3	475±28	2524±841	2.7±8.0
NZ3	63-90	21	957±375	3212±1703	3.0±4.4
	90-125	7	1214±233	4116±1580	5.4±1.5
	125-180	8	1676±303	7924±2458	2.1±0.4
	180-250	8	1483±403	5580±3031	3.5±4.3
NZ 4	63-90	5	978±387	3936±1354	1.6±0.3
NZ 5	63-90	3	602±57	2646±294	2.1±0.1
	90-125	3	613±15	3901±2051	2.5±0.6

Table S3. Measured equivalent doses using both pIRIR protocols along with the results of the recycling and recuperation tests

Sample code	Protocol	Measured equivalent dose (Gy)	Recycling	Recuperation (%)
NZ 2	pIRIR ₂₂₅	64±2	0.97±0.01	1.6±0.3
	pIRIR ₂₉₀	83±3	0.93±0.01	1.4±0.1
NZ 3	pIRIR ₂₂₅	67±1	1.00±0.02	1.3±0.3
	pIRIR ₂₉₀	86±4	0.98±0.03	1.4±0.2
NZ 4	pIRIR ₂₂₅	84±3	0.99±0.01	1.1±0.2
	pIRIR ₂₉₀	123±7	0.93±0.01	1.1±0.1
NZ 5	pIRIR ₂₂₅	92±3	0.98±0.01	1.7±0.4
	pIRIR ₂₉₀	120±6	0.99±0.02	1.5±0.1

Table S4. Residual doses measured using pIRIR₂₂₅ and pIRIR₂₉₀ protocols after one month of bleaching.

Sample code	Protocol	Residual dose (Gy)
NZ 2	pIRIR ₂₂₅	3.3±0.4
	pIRIR ₂₉₀	8.3±0.5
NZ 3	pIRIR ₂₂₅	3.7±0.3
	pIRIR ₂₉₀	4.1±0.6
NZ 4	pIRIR ₂₂₅	3.7±0.2
	pIRIR ₂₉₀	13.6±2.5
NZ 5	pIRIR ₂₂₅	3.4±0.5
	pIRIR ₂₉₀	10.9±1.4

Table S5. g-values measured on polymineral fine grains using pIRIR₂₂₅ protocol.

Sample code	aliq	g-value (%/decade)	Average g-value (%/decade)
NZ 2	aliq 1	-0.93±-0.68	0.44±0.69
	aliq 2	1.05±0.69	
	aliq 3	1.21±0.69	
NZ 4	aliq 1	2.87±0.74	2.28±0.44
	aliq 2	1.42±0.72	
	aliq 3	2.55±0.72	
NZ 5	aliq 1	1.09±0.66	0.88±0.12
	aliq 2	0.88±0.69	
	aliq 3	0.68±0.66	

a.

b.

c.

d.

Figure S1. Comparison between the TL glow curves recorded with a ramp heating of 5 °C/sto 500°C for different aliquots of sample NZ3 (63-90 μm) and END 1.1 (63-90 μm). END 1.1 is considered a representative sample due to its ideal OSL properties (for more details see Tecsá et al., 2020). (a) TL signal recorded for sample NZ 3 immediately after an irradiation with 100 Gy; (b) same as (a) but with a preheat of 10 s at 220 °C inserted before measurement; (c) TL signal recorded for sample END 1.2 immediately after an irradiation with 100 Gy; (d) same as (c) but with a preheat of 10 s at 220 °C inserted before measurement. Please note that these signals are representative for samples that have not been previously annealed.

Figure S2. The effect of annealing on OSL and low temperature TL signals. (a) represents the TL response to 100 Gy recorded during first annealing of the sample in the dose recovery experiment denoted as experiment (ii) in the main text. (b) represents the TL recorded after 100 Gy in the subsequent annealing steps. (c) TL recorded during the preheat in the dose recovery test with no previous annealing on 3 distinct aliquots. (d) TL recorded during the dose recovery test with previous annealing (experiment (ii) in the main text) on 3 distinct aliquots. (e) OSL response to 100 Gy recorded on three distinct aliquots in a dose recovery test with no annealing. (f) OSL response to 100 Gy recorded on three distinct aliquots in a dose recovery test with previous annealing (experiment (ii) in the main text).

a.

b.

Figure S3. Residual doses as function of measured equivalent dose using (a) pIRIR₂₂₅ and (b) pIRIR₂₉₀ protocols. The aliquots used for residual dose measurements were exposed to window light for 1 month.

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Figure S4. Results of the fading rate measurements on individual aliquots of 4-11 μm polymineral material using pIRIR₂₂₅ protocol on sample (a,b,c) NZ 2, (d,e,f) NZ 4 and (g,h,i) NZ 5. The signals were read after a maximum delay of 38 days. A number of 4 consecutive prompt read-outs were carried out before signal measurement after delay and two/three consecutive prompts read-outs were added after different delays times. The signal intensity of the first instantaneous read-out is represented with filled symbols.

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